

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Multimedia educational and methodological complex as a means of forming sociolinguistic competence

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Abstract

Relevance of the problem

In order to achieve the desired goal of teaching a foreign language in the unity of its linguistic and sociolinguistic components, there is a need to use modern multimedia technologies in the educational process. And this, in turn, forces teachers to look for new teaching methods, to use teaching aids in combination with authentic Internet resources, to fill in the missing natural language environment.

The aim of the research is to create a multimedia educational and methodological complex that promotes the development of the sociolinguistic component of foreign language communicative competence in the process of teaching French.

Within the framework of the study, the methods of linguistic and methodological analysis, comparison and analogy, description and synthesis, as well as experimental verification were used.

The methodological basis of the study was the provisions of the communicative, competence-based and socio-cultural approaches.

The result of the study was the creation of a multimedia educational and methodological complex as the main means of developing the sociolinguistic component of foreign language communicative competence, the identification of its constituent elements, the analysis of the structural components of the virtual language environment, as well as examples of some Internet resources that are valuable for teaching French.

The developed materials can be used as a basis for creating such multimedia textbooks in order to form other components of foreign language communicative competence, as well as for creating a virtual language environment when learning French, which is the **practical significance** of the study.

Keywords: sociolinguistic competence, virtual language environment, multimedia complex

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Published by Moscow City University and peer-reviewed under responsibility of TSNI-2021
(Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity)

Introduction

The processes of informatization of society affected all spheres of human activity, not sparing education, which subsequently led to the modernization of education and the reorientation of the goals and content of the educational process in general, and in the field of teaching foreign languages, in particular.

The modern information society requires educational institutions to train not only highly qualified, morally and spiritually developed specialists, but also specialists who are ready for intercultural dialogue in the information space.

These social factors contributed to the creation and active integration of new educational technologies aimed at improving the quality of the educational process, optimizing the costs of its provision, as well as increasing the level of general culture of the younger generation (Fateev, 2011).

Based on the opinion of A. M. Fateev, we, following him, believe that in the modernization of the educational process, the main direction is the preparation of students to participate in all areas of the information society. The main task of modernizing education is the formation of an educational space and the creation of educational environments based on the synthesis of pedagogical technologies and informatization of education for the disclosure of educational potential and personal development (Fateev, 2011).

According to the scientist, within the framework of informatization of the educational process, it is important that the methods and tools are relevant and consistent with the stage of informatization, and it is also necessary that new strategies for the use of multimedia tools are created for the effectiveness of the educational process (Fateev, 2011).

Purpose and objectives of the study

As for the modernization of foreign language education, an impressive theoretical basis for communicative learning in the context of intercultural dialogue has been developed in this area, methodological technologies have been created and applied in practice, embodying the ideas of communicative-activity and socio-cultural approaches.

Despite this, research in the field of foreign language teaching methods reveals the ambiguity of the intentions of the modern school in the formation of a personality that is consistent with its time, ready and capable of a dialogue of cultures, has the necessary level of language proficiency, and the sociolinguistic component of foreign language communicative competence, in particular.

Literature review

After analyzing these studies on the formation of foreign language communicative competence (FLCC) and its components, we observe that the Methodists began to pay more attention to the individual components of the FLCC, reflecting national-cultural features of communication.

Highlighting a significant component of foreign language communicative competence, methodologists give a leading place to the sociolinguistic component, since it includes not only knowledge of the language code, but also readiness, ability to choose, transform and use foreign language means, based on the nature and context of communication, taking into account the norms of politeness, communication registers, dialects, accents, linguistic markers of social relations and expressions of folk wisdom (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages, 2020).

Mastering a language means mastering certain patterns of action that are specific to a particular communication situation (Santos, Buson & Chevrot, 2018). French authors B. Lallement, and N. Pierret, analyzing the main components of sociolinguistic competence based on the French language, distinguish the following elements in its structure: registers, dialects, accents, norms of politeness and etiquette, and expressions of folk wisdom (Lallement & Pierret, 2015).

The sociolinguistic component of the foreign language communicative competence, having a multicomponent nature, requires the gradual development of its components, which, in turn, leads to the

need to use modern multimedia technologies in the educational process.

This thesis has been confirmed in French didactic manuals, the main purpose of which is to attract relevant authentic Internet resources to increase the motivation of students, as well as to constantly update the taught material (Denier, 2020), (Cuq & Gruca, 2017), (Jeffroy, 2015), (Barrière, Emile & Gella, 2011).

The analysis of the research revealed that the attention of scientists is focused on solving common problems of the use of ICT in the educational process. We note the works of Shatokhina I. V. (2001), Vorotneva E. A.(2002), Pugina O. A.(2002), Zaitseva E. N.(2003), Opryshko A. A. (2004), Smirnova S. A. (2004), Romanovskaya O. E.(2005), Fritsko Zh. S. (2006), Ivanova N. V.(2007), Matienko A.V. (2009), Khlybova M. A.(2011), Terechik L. B.(2012).

Nevertheless, despite the existing research, a number of questions concerning the development of the sociolinguistic component of the FLCC remain unexplored. We did not find any works devoted to the development of the sociolinguistic component of the FLCC using multimedia technologies as a tool for teaching a foreign language.

The considered examples of dissertation research support the conclusion that the issue of creating a new effective, time-appropriate means for teaching the French language, namely, a multimedia educational and methodological complex for the development of the sociolinguistic component of the FLCC is not sufficiently studied, and is an urgent problem.

Methodology

The aim of the research is to create a multimedia educational and methodological complex that promotes the development of the sociolinguistic component of foreign language communicative competence in the process of teaching French.

Within the framework of the study, the methods of linguistic and methodological analysis, comparison and analogy, description and synthesis, as well as experimental verification were used.

The methodological basis of the study was the provisions of the communicative, competence-based and socio-cultural approaches.

The experimental basis of the study was the 2nd-year students of the Institute of Foreign Languages of VSPU, in the number of 57 people.

Stages of the experiment.

The ascertaining stage, during which a cross-section was carried out, with the aim of establishing the initial level of development of the sociolinguistic component of the students' IQ before the experiment.

The formative stage is the experiment itself, within the framework of which the research result was achieved;

The control stage, at which the final cross-section was implemented, aimed at determining the level of development of the sociolinguistic component of the students' FLCC after the experiment.

Results

Having considered the linguodidactic and methodological foundations for the development of the sociolinguistic component of the ICK, as well as identifying the lack of use of modern ICTs in the educational process, we obtained the following results:

1. The multimedia teaching aids promote bright presentation, strong consolidation and development of new language and speech material with sociolinguistic content.

Each module includes a specific set of exercises aimed at a particular key language or speech material, as well as a bank of role-playing games that help to increase the motivation of students. The virtual core of the multimedia complex is a bank of authentic Internet resources available to any user, as well as valuable for learning French, increasing the motivation of students and reflecting the realities of the life of native speakers (Dakhia Mounir, 2020).

A step-by-step and consistent methodology for the development of the sociolinguistic component based on a multimedia educational and methodological complex in the process of teaching French is carried out in

three stages:

1) the stage of mastering sociolinguistic knowledge (the norms of speech etiquette adopted in the country of the language being studied; the norms of using the language in different communicative situations, situational variants of expressing the same communicative intention);

2) the stage of mastering communication skills and the ability to learn and apply language parameters: social relations, belonging to an ethnic group, profession, place of residence, formulas of speech communication that contribute to the achievement of communicative intent, based on the communication situation; register, socio-cultural conditions of language use; differences in language signals between traditions, values adopted in the two cultures;

3) the stage of development of sociolinguistic and speech skills, as well as the need to learn French and acquire knowledge of culture (Zakharova, Milovanova, 2018).

To achieve the main goal of the study, we chose the classification of D. I. Izarenkov, which contains the following exercises: presentational, constructive, reconstructive, transformational, search-associative, analytical-structuring, modeling, and constructive-transformational-combining exercises (Izarenkov, 1994). The multimedia complex, in addition to the presentation, consolidation and development of the main language and speech material, is equipped with tasks to control the formation of the sociolinguistic component of the IQC, which appear in the form of tests and creative productive tasks (essays on problematic topics).

2. The multimedia educational and methodological complex includes three structural elements, namely, linguistic, representing language, speech material, lexical and grammatical minima, situations and speech norms of behavior in them:

1. Introduction of someone to someone.

2. Expression of gratitude.

3. Polite refusal.

4. Apologies, etc. Je vous présente Monsieur / Madame ... Permettez-moi de vous présenter... / Merci beaucoup. / Je vous remercie. / Non merci, ce n'est pas la peine;

5. Social conventions and rituals:

a. Invitation.

b. Congratulations. etc. Compliments ! Félicitations !; phraseological units: La fin justifie les moyens. Voilà où git le lièvre! "That's where the dog is buried!" Il ne lui arrive pas à la cheville-He is no match for him; proverbs and sayings: "A cheval donné, on ne regarde pas les dents." (Lallement & Pierret, 2015).

The basic topics at the initial stage of learning French are: "Family", "Friendship", "Description of appearance", "Daily routine", "Study", "Housing", "Hobbies" and " Weather"(Rolle-Harold & Roesch, 2020).

The psychological component of the training content includes the development of the following skills:

1) use linguistic markers of social relations of communicants, their background, residence, employment;

2) use models, verbal communication, implementing any communicative intention, according to the situation of communication;

3) analysis and selection of the register communication, depending on the sociocultural conditions of language use;

4) applying language signals differences between traditions, values, beliefs (Les valeurs républicaines, 2020), adopted in the native and foreign cultures.

The methodological component is the acquisition of skills:

1) to determine and change registers in the context of changing communication situations;

2) to differentiate stylistic variants of speech units of etiquette;

3) to understand and correctly evaluate socio-culturally colored lexical units in authentic speech; 4) to analyze the characteristics of speech behavior and its correction, avoiding possible communicative errors;

5) to analyze authentic materials to obtain sociolinguistic information about France;

6) identify the linguistic characteristics of a person, in view of his origin, residence, social significance, and employment (Cuq & Gruca, 2017).

3. The main problem, whose solution provides the process of development of the sociolinguistic

component of the BCI-based multimedia educational-methodical complex:

- systematization of multimedia means of learning a foreign language, highlight their key benefits to the educational process, as well as determining evaluation parameters and selection of the linguistic quality of a computer-based training materials for learning the French language;

- * modeling of the virtual language environment (in typical communication situations);

- * development of a multimedia educational and methodological complex based on the modular principle of teaching and including such methodological tools as: a bank of authentic and semi-authentic texts of different genres, Internet resources, communication games and a set of exercises;

- * organization of educational activities of students to acquire sociolinguistic knowledge, develop communication skills and abilities, as well as the formation of readiness and abilities for intercultural communication in the framework of three stages: mastering knowledge, developing skills and improving skills.

4. Before the introduction of the multimedia educational and methodological complex, a survey was conducted, according to the results of which the students' readiness to use computer training programs in the classroom and at home was stated (86%).

5. A pedagogical clarifying natural experiment was conducted in order to test the hypothesis put forward by us, which postulates that the introduction of a multimedia complex will serve as an effective means of forming the sociolinguistic component of the IQC and will have a positive impact on learning outcomes.

6. Five groups of criteria for the level of formation of the sociolinguistic component of the IQC are identified, based on the content units of the cognitive, procedural and personal components: 1) formulas of speech etiquette; 2) expressions of folk wisdom; 3) linguistic markers of social relations; 4) registers of communication; 5) stylistic variants of etiquette speech units.

7. A ascertaining cross-section was carried out, the results of which showed an insufficient level of formation of the sociolinguistic component of the IQC.

8. Experimental training was carried out according to the methodology created by us. After completing this training, the students wrote a final cross-section, the results of which were compared with the data of the ascertaining cross-section.

9. We compared the average scores of the five criteria for the level of satisfaction with the development of the sociolinguistic component of the IQ of primary school students, and concluded that the average score on the criteria increased by 1.8 times after the experiment, and as a result of testing the methodology we created.

10. The result of the experiment was:

- a) a significant increase in the level of development of sociolinguistic skills and abilities;

- b) immersion of students in a virtual language environment, which made up for the lack of a natural language environment and filled in the gaps in the printed QMS;

- c) expansion of sociolinguistic knowledge.

The experimental data confirm that the use of multimedia educational-methodical complex has a significant influence on the development of the sociolinguistic component of the FLCC by creating a virtual language environment and immersion in her students, but also positively affects the dynamics of development of sociolinguistic knowledge, as part of the sociolinguistic component of the FLCC.

Discussions

1. Within the framework of foreign language communicative competence, the sociolinguistic component is relevant for us, since it includes not only linguistic, but also sociolinguistic, including the readiness, ability to choose, transform and use foreign language means, depending on the situation and context of communication.

For the development of the sociolinguistic component, we have chosen a multimedia educational and methodological complex as the main means to achieve this goal. By this term, we understand, firstly, a complete set of educational and methodological materials necessary for conducting all types of classes in the discipline "Foreign Language", taking into account the specifics of all forms and technologies of

teaching; Secondly, the main means of teaching a foreign language in the context of informatization of the educational process, in which training is conducted on the basis of traditional teaching aids, using authentic Internet resources that create a virtual language environment necessary for the harmonious development of not only the sociolinguistic component, but also the formation of foreign language communicative competence in general (Zakharova, 2019).

2. The virtual language environment is understood by us as a language environment achieved by using ICT and Internet resources, in order to immerse oneself in an adequate authentic language environment outside the territory of the functioning of a foreign language. The virtual language environment is formed on the basis of information of a cultural, ethnic and social nature, which is valuable in the formation of sociolinguistic competence, as part of intercultural communicative competence. The creation of such an environment can be based on a multimedia educational and methodological complex, including special tasks and exercises based on the use of the socio-cultural realities of an authentic language environment (Zakharova, 2019).

In our opinion, the following elements should be included in the structure of the virtual language environment

- * A multimedia educational and methodological complex that promotes the presentation, consolidation and development of new language and speech material with sociolinguistic content.

- * The virtual core of the multimedia complex is a bank of Internet resources that are available to any user, as well as continuously updated, thus representing value for learning French.

As the main Internet resources used for teaching a foreign language and for creating a virtual language environment, it is necessary to mention the online resource created in cooperation with the French television TV5 Monde and the educational portal Polar FLE.

1. "Première classe avec TV5 Monde" is a training program for both beginners and advanced level (level of knowledge of AI A1-B2), created in tandem with TV5 Monde— an international French-language TV company. This resource presents various topics to students, such as " Dating", " Hobbies", " Housing", " Study", "Food". The presence of these topics is methodically justified, because they are included in the lexical minimum of the basic level of the AI. This resource is designed in such a way that the student can independently choose the appropriate language of hints, which eliminates the difficulties of understanding at the initial stage of learning French.

This portal has a number of undoubted advantages. Since it is built in cooperation with a television channel, the presentation and primary consolidation of vocabulary, grammar is very vivid, memorable, through videos accompanied by interactive exercises, logically arranged according to the degree of complexity, related thematically and complementary to each other. This creates stable associative connections, which allows the material to be permanently fixed in the memory of the trainees. Continuous work with the same material, but in different blocks and at different stages, undoubtedly allows you to intensify the work of memory. The subject matter of video and audio fragments imitates the situations of real life of the French, the language and speech material offered to students is relevant and authentic, thereby contributing to the formation of sociolinguistic competencies. An important disadvantage of this resource is the lack of a dictionary, as well as linguistic and socio-linguistic commentary.

2. The online resource "Polar FLE", developed by French language teachers Anna and Thierry Perrault, at the International Center for the Study of Foreign Languages, which is a partner of the French Campus, is a specially created program for teaching French as a foreign language, which is different from others. The detective story attracts students with its plot and active involvement in the game form. The student acts as an assistant detective, collects evidence, interrogates suspects, searches for the culprit and solves the crime. This portal is publicly accessible, is important for all levels of French language proficiency and is designed for 50 hours.

It is obvious that the involvement in the story has a positive effect on the motivation and interest of the user, and also indicates the high technical and ergonomic quality of the product, since this resource is most pronounced "multimedia" presentation of educational material, i.e. the presentation of different information formats in one media source.

At the same time, from a methodological point of view, this resource has a number of significant

drawbacks: a meager topic that narrows learning opportunities; the lack of a dictionary and control over the assimilation of the acquired knowledge makes it difficult to self-reflect and monitor one's own progress in mastering the material.

Despite a number of these shortcomings, both programs can serve as content for a virtual language environment.

3. Online resource *Bibliothèques sans Frontières-Les voyageurs du Numérique*. This platform is completely open and free to use. It includes an infinite variety of literature available for use in foreign language classes, and also has didactic value for building lessons using various multimedia, as it has a guide for creating such classes.

* A bank of role-playing games aimed at simulating real communication situations, developing improvisation and adapting to changing conditions and situations of communication (Branellec-Sorensen & Chalaron, 2017).

Here are some examples of educational role-playing games. As part of the study of the lexical topic "Logement / Housing", the main goal of the role-playing game is the formation of speech skills and abilities on a given topic.

Task 1. Read, restore the logical order of the replicas, role play this dialogue.

Chez un agent immobilier :

M. Ruyer : Bonjour. Qu'est-ce que vous désirez ?

M. Ruyer : Très bien, vous voulez un appartement meublé ?

M. Dupont : Je cherche un F3 meublé dans un quartier calme.

M. Ruyer : il y en a un dans la rue de l'Université dans une maison à 5 étages.

M. Ruyer : Au revoir.

M. Dupont : Oui, et avec tout confort.

M. Ruyer : au quatrième. C'est un immeuble moderne, avec tout confort nécessaire, il y a un ascenseur, un digicode, un interphone...

M. Dupont : est-ce qu'il y a un vide-ordures ?

M. Ruyer : oui, bien sûr.

M. Dupont : Bon. Merci. Je vais parler à ma femme. Je vais revenir plus tard.

M. Dupont : cet appartement, il est à quel étage ?

Task 2. Listen to the dialog and fill in the gaps.

Task 3. You moved to live in Paris and turned to a real estate agency in search of an apartment. Play the «In a real estate agency» dialog.

Simulation of real situations in a game form, through variative-situational speech exercises, contributes not only to the development of the studied language and speech material in a situational context, but also to the consistent formation of sociolinguistic competence.

Conclusion

After analyzing the literature and developing a model of the multimedia complex, as well as developing the idea of the possibility of creating a virtual language environment, we came to the conclusion that the need to use additional means of teaching a foreign language, along with the already traditional teaching aids, is an urgent problem.

The implementation of the training was facilitated by the means of electronic educational platforms *Parlons français, c'est facile-TV5Monde, Bonjour de France, Français facile, Podcast français facile, Français avec Pierre: Apprendre le Français c'est facile!* Audio-Lingua, Polar FLE.

The main advantages of using a multimedia educational and methodological complex for the development of the sociolinguistic component of the FLCC are: 1) creation of a complete picture of the material being studied; 2) formation of basic knowledge in the module; 3) formation of independent work skills; 4)

development of students' needs for productive use of information; 5) development of memory, voluntary attention; 6) formation of students' logical thinking.

After ascertaining the slice according to the following criteria level of development of the sociolinguistic component of FLCC (1) formula of speech etiquette; 2) expressions of folk wisdom; 3) linguistic markers of social relations; 4) registers of communication; 5) stylistic variants of speech etiquette units) was found insufficient level of development of the sociolinguistic component of the FLCC, the average score was equal to 2.2, which is an indicator of "below average".

After the introduction and work with the multimedia educational and methodological complex, the level of development of the sociolinguistic component of the FLCC, on average, increased 1.8 times.

Summing up the above, it should be noted that a multimedia educational-methodical complex, complementing traditional learning tools, gives students the necessary topical knowledge not only about the language but also about the realities of life and culture of native speakers.

Using this multimedia educational and methodological complex, supplemented by Internet resources and multimedia technologies, the student, immersed in a virtual language environment, has the opportunity to harmoniously develop the sociolinguistic component, and foreign language communicative competence, in general. Since ignoring this component leads to gaps in the field of etiquette, norms of politeness, paremiological fund, and to the uneven formation of foreign language communicative competence, in general.

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